

Psychological Factors of Suicide

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Abstract

It is understood that suicide is a major health problem and the leading cause of death worldwide. Because, this subject, which needs much more work, needs to be explained, although it is essential to be developed in the literature. Recent reports report that approximately one million people die by suicide each year, representing the annual global age-standardized suicide rate of 11.4 (15.0 for men and 8.0 for women) per 100,000 population. Considering a time perspective from 2000 to 2016, there has been a 30% increase in suicide rates by age. These ratios are just the tip of an iceberg. There are more who try suicide every year. A cautious estimate shows that more than 20 million people engage in suicidal behavior each year. In addition, considering the WHO's announcement that suicide rates will exceed the one million marks in the next 15 years, it is predicted that suicide rates will increase in the future. Behind every suicide and attempt, there is a long-term struggle of these individuals, their experiences of trauma and distress among their relatives and friends. However, preventing suicide is a global priority. As clinicians and researchers, we must make every effort to find, intervene, and after preventing suicidal behavior. Above all, our mission is to advance our knowledge by understanding the mechanisms, factors, and facilitators of suicide from interdisciplinary perspectives.

Keywords: *suicide, suicide psychology, reasons for suicide, suicide in psychology, solutions to suicide*

1. Introduction

A review of the relationship between rumination and suicidal behavior decides the relationship between the findings and the main psychological risk and protective factors for suicidal ideation and suicidal behavior:

With regard to preventing people at risk from attempting suicide, findings from a meta-analysis of cognitive behavioral therapies for suicidal behavior showed a statistically significant effect of cognitive behavioral therapy for reducing the rate of suicide attempts; however, the researchers demonstrate a publication bias in this regard, with smaller studies reporting more positive effect sizes and no published study findings showing negative effects for any intervention, like a funnel plot of published studies with near-zero centers.

These thoughts include the more specific consequences of suicidal ideation; this means deliberately considering ending one's own life; suicide plan, which refers to the formulation of a specific plan for the individual to end their own life; and suicide attempt refers to engaging in potentially self-harming behavior with at least some intention to die as a result of the behavior.¹ Recent research suggests that social dimensions of perfectionism increase suicide risk by

¹ That is, it is not clear why the factors work together to increase the risk of this behavior.

promoting a sense of social disconnection, which is consistent with the integrated motivational-volitional model and the interpersonal theory of suicide.

The big five personality dimensions: neuroticism, extraversion, agreeableness, openness to experience, and conscientiousness are generally associated with high neuroticism and low extraversion with suicidal ideation, attempts, and completions. More models have been proposed, most emphasizing the interaction between predisposing and accelerating factors. The most key factor leading to suicide is unbearable mental pain.

More studies have emphasized the importance of psychic pain as the primary facilitator of suicidal ideation and behavior. In the Israel MSSA (Medically Serious Suicide Attempts) project, Levi-Belz and colleagues have shown that poor character, along with more relevant factors, can ease suicidal behavior more lethal.²

Finally, in the review by Conti et al, the authors systematically review the associations between eating disorders and suicidal ideation and suicide attempts.

More reviewed articles focus on finding risk factors in childhood. In terms of the link between suicidal exposure and risk of suicidal behavior, Stanley et al reported that firefighters who took part in a suicide call were more likely to report suicidal ideation and attempts.

2. Most Suicidal People Do Not Get Treatment and Little Evidence Is Available for Suicide

The effectiveness of the interventions received highlights the enormous importance of future work to develop psychological treatments for people at risk for suicidal behavior. Although more risk factors have been found for suicidal behavior, suicide is when an individual deliberately ends their own life. The development of more innovative brief psychosocial interventions (using a range of delivery methods) to reduce suicidal ideation, attempts, and suicide increases the risk of suicidal and self-harming suicidal behavior and suicidal clusters. In addition, none of the studies of psychologists and psychiatrists have evaluated the relationship between exposure to suicide and their own risk of suicidal thoughts and behavior. Improving understanding of these issues can help clinicians and researchers create specific prevention strategies and methods that will ultimately help reduce suicide rates worldwide and find psychological relief for all those struggling with suicidal ideation and behavior. Correlates of suicide ideation and attempt among youth living in the slums of physical activity and reduced rates of hopelessness, depression, and suicidal behavior among college students. This is not a final and comprehensive report of available knowledge, but rather an introduction to the psychological factors involved in suicide.

Prevalence estimates vary widely by country; however, once present, the characteristics of suicidal behavior are quite consistent in different countries.³ Social isolation and lack of social

² Psychological Factors In the last century, the contribution of psychological factors (both individual and social) to suicide and suicide risk has been recognized. These include attentional bias, impulsivity, problem-solving, and decision-making deficits.

³ The risk of non-fatal suicidal behavior is increased in younger people, women (who have higher rates of non-fatal suicidality than men, but men are more likely to die by suicide), unmarried people, and people who commit suicide.

support are set up correlates of suicide risk and are important components of contemporary models of suicidal behavior. Because the nature of the relationship with the person who died by suicide for mental health professionals is different from that of first responders, we might expect the effects of suicidal exposure on these two groups to be different. The Suicidal Behavior Questionnaire Revised SBQ-R showed that suicide measures such as IPTS were not evaluated between mental health professionals' exposure to suicide. Fearlessness and insensitivity to pain Since suicidal behavior often involves inflicting physical pain on the body, suicide risk and both pain sensitivity and tolerance and fearlessness of death have been studied. Although earlier theories focused on individual psychological factors, they did not explain why most people with suicidal ideation do not try suicide.⁴ Management of suicidal behavior in patients may manifest as increased alertness when assessing suicide, or systematic referral of a patient to another colleague (for a second evaluation), or complete avoidance of treating patients at risk for suicide. predicts future suicide tries beyond other factors, including prior knowledge of suicidal behavior. More evidence suggests that certain forms of cognitive and behavioral therapy that directly target suicidal thoughts and behaviors may reduce the risk of re-attempts in people who have tried suicide. However, if a person with a high suicidal desire gains the ability to try suicide, the risk of a serious suicide attempt increases.

According to the theory, exposure to and meeting earlier painful experiences increases an individual's tolerance for the physical-painful aspects of self-harm through habit processes. Understanding the psychological processes underlying both suicidal ideation and the decision to act on suicidal thoughts is particularly important because interventions should aim to address the first occurrence of suicidal ideation before going ahead to a suicide attempt. Collaborative assessment and management of suicide is a clinical intervention designed to improve the therapeutic alliance and reduce the risk of suicidal behavior. perfectionism Increasing evidence suggests that perfectionism is associated with suicidal ideation and suicide attempts, but few prospective clinical studies have been conducted. A recent systematic review suggests a link between psychological distress experienced in these occupations and higher suicide rates. Exposure to suicide can personally affect first responders and mental health professionals and affect their professional practice. Despite research into resilience (“It is defined as “the qualities that enable a person to be successful in the face of difficulties”). Some evidence suggests that resilience has a protective effect on suicidal ideation in military personnel, alcohol and illicit drug abusers, and prisoners, but its effect on suicide attempts or deaths by suicide is largely unknown. The recent review by Dutheil Aubert highlighted the lack of research examining the etiology and transition from suicidal ideation to suicide attempt among healthcare professionals. Psychological Theories of Suicidal Behavior The origins of recent theories can be traced back to Freud, but continued research into suicide did not begin in earnest until the 1950s and has grown significantly over the past 25 years. Bullying victimization as a predictor of suicidal ideation and suicide attempt among senior high school students in Ghana: Results from the 2012 Ghana Global School-Based Health Survey. Findings in research using the implicit association evaluate this association differentiated suicidal attempters from distressed people who did not try emergency psychiatric treatment (i.e., suicide attempters responded faster when matching death and self-related stimuli than they did [measured in milliseconds]).

⁴ These more recent mixed findings suggest that while hopelessness is important in the development of suicidal ideation (consistent with theoretical models), other factors may be more useful in predicting actual suicide attempts or deaths.

Such factors include exposure to the suicidal behavior of others, impulsivity, and access to suicide tools.⁵

3. Risk factors for suicide

The attempting group also scored significantly ($p > 0.001$) higher on each measure of risk factor for suicide, namely hopelessness, mental pain, and depression, compared with the non-intervention group. changes in pain sensitivity, suicidal ideation or suicidal ideation or behavior; The issue of how these changes change as a function of the suicide history and throughout life needs to be clarified. For example, less than 5% of people hospitalized for treatment of a mood disorder die by suicide; most people with psychiatric disorders will not die by suicide and will not experience suicidal behavior.

The motivational stage finds the factors that govern the development of suicidal ideation and intention, while the volitional stage outlines the factors that decide whether an individual attempts suicide. In the Israel MSSA (Medically Serious Suicide Attempts) project, Levi-Belz and colleagues proved that weak self-disclosure could ease more lethal suicidal behavior, with more factors involved. Psychophysiological stress response Causes of a Person's Symptoms A distinction has been noted between reflective rumination, in which a person dwells on their symptoms, and reflective thinking, in which a person considers the causes of their symptoms and workable solutions.

Rumination has also been associated with increased symptoms of depression, hopelessness, and impaired problem solving; An important goal for future research is to clarify how these factors may work together to increase the risk of suicidal behavior. Consistent with these theories, subjective feeling of lack of social connection and inhibition of belonging was associated with suicidal ideation and suicide attempts. Findings from more studies have shown that self-reported impulsivity is associated with suicidal ideation, suicide attempts, and suicide deaths. Our review highlights more its effects on exposure to suicide and how this may contribute to the negative mental health outcomes associated with an increased risk of suicide. From a clinical point of view, the importance of being able to make predictions about suicidal transitions can be explained by the cubic suicide model, Shneidman (1985), the combination of pressure (stress), pain (psychic pain), and uneasiness can be explained by suicide risk.

4. Zhao and Shai's Study

Zhao and Shai's study reveals that students' attitudes towards suicidal behavior and attitudes towards suicide survivors play as a mediator between self-efficacy and self-evaluations in managing happiness among college students. Second, the integrated motivational-volitional model of suicidal behavior conceptualizes suicide as a behavior (rather than a byproduct of mental disorders) that develops through motivational and volitional stages. This model integrates key factors from earlier theories into a detailed map of the suicide process, from

⁵ The Median score was 63 ± 0.48 and the Median score was 1 (min = 0, max = 1), while the Mean score of those who did not try suicide was 0.11 ± 0.31 and the Median score was 0 (0.1). The difference was significant ($U = 214,248.00$, $p < 0.001$). The effect size using Cohen's d is medium (0.72).

thoughts to suicidal actions.⁶ Psychological treatment trials are necessary to reduce suicidal ideation, attempts, and suicide. Psychologists and Psychiatrists Eight of the eleven articles examining the effects of suicidal exposure reported the prevalence of patient suicide focusing on psychologists and psychiatrists, with 31.5–92% of these professionals having experienced at least one client suicide.

Suicide risk is not only related to a psychiatric disorder (stressor) but also to another diathesis (i.e., a tendency to experience more suicidal thoughts or impulsivity). "Can post discharge follow-up contacts prevent suicide and suicidal behavior? A review of the evidence". Depression and hopelessness as risk factors for suicide ideation, tries and death: meta-analysis of longitudinal studies. It requires larger-scale studies testing psychological models and risk factors to predict suicide attempt and death.⁷ The lack of studies targeting mental health outcomes after suicide suggests that suicide researchers may not pay enough attention to suicide risk among health professionals and may be better equipped because they are trained to supply support in these situations.

5. Psychological Factors

While psychological factors such as risk-taking and decision making can influence the risk of other causes of death (for example, heart disease and cancer), suicide is perhaps the most directly affected cause of death by psychological factors because a person makes an informed decision. More recently, in a small study of suicidal attempters, hopelessness did not significantly predict future suicide attempts at a 4-year follow-up when history of suicide attempts and entrapment were included in the analysis. For balance, however, most people with psychiatric disorders never commit suicide (that is, experience suicidal thoughts, try suicide, or die by suicide). Scientific Literature The scientific literature has focused on the study of exposure to suicide among different health professionals, but less attention has been paid to first responders, despite some limited, mainly quantitative research. While dissolving the buffers as well as the risks of suicide can be complex, the model offers the conceptualization of suicide from a multifaceted approach integrating individual, social, and familial factors that may be associated with suicide occurrence, thus supplying a broader environmental context interpretation for better understanding and clarification of risk factors. First, Joiner's theory of interpersonal suicide assumes the coexistence of elevated levels of perceived burden (i.e., feeling a burden to others) and low levels of belonging (i.e., feeling alienated or not), and being hopeless that these states will not change, suicidal desire (i.e., suicidal ideation) leads to the development of thought.

6. Psychological Autopsy Studies Psychological

⁶ Stressful, humiliating or defeating conditions are considered the most important within the integrated motivational-volitional model. Role of social support in adolescent suicidal ideation and suicide attempts.

⁷ About one-third of people who are considering suicide will go on to try suicide, and more than 60% of these transitions will occur within the first year after the first onset of suicidal ideation. While research to date has supplied most insights into the complex effects of suicide exposure on mental health professionals, limited research has been done on the impact of suicide exposure on first responders.

Psychological Autopsy Studies Psychological autopsy studies, which collected information about the deceased from more informants, have played a key role in understanding the risk factors for suicide. This scoping review highlights more of the gaps in the research foundation about exposure to suicide in mental health professionals and first responders. Suicidal Thoughts The science of psychology is well placed to understand why some people try suicide while others do not. Consistent with the interpersonal theory of suicide, the interaction of perceived belonging and burden is predictive of suicidal ideation even after controlling for depressive symptoms. Researchers also relied heavily on self-report observational studies; multi-method approaches, with an increasing focus on basic science experimental research, will help uncover the mechanisms by which factors increase or decrease suicide risk. The integrated motivational-volitional model of suicidal behavior is a diathesis-stress model that decides the components of suicide.⁸ Traumatic Cases Unfortunately, adverse life events can affect well-being at any age, and traumatic events in adulthood (for example, physical or sexual abuse; death of a loved one; disasters or accidents; exposure to war or other violence) may also increase. Study findings showed a dose-response relationship between the number of adverse events and the risk of later suicidal behavior; again, physical and sexual abuse seem to carry the highest risk for both the onset and persistence of suicidal behavior. Joiner's theory of interpersonal suicide highlights two main interpersonal structures—perceived burden and denied belonging—as critical characteristics that can lead to suicidal ideation and eventual suicide. Joiner's theory of interpersonal suicide highlights two main interpersonal constructs—perceived burden and denied belonging—as critical characteristics that can lead to suicidal ideation and eventual suicide. An interesting finding from the review is that mental health professionals do not have self-assessments of mental health and suicide. The lack of data on mental health outcomes makes it impossible to compare the effects of exposure to the effects of suicide on mental health professionals with those of first responders. The effects on suicide risk following suicidal grief are discussed in detail by Pitman and colleagues. Considering the scarcity of research on protective factors, efforts have been made to find factors that supply resilience by resisting the risk of suicide in the face of difficulties. While some evidence suggests that different forms of cognitive and behavioral therapy may reduce the risk of suicide attempts, there is virtually no evidence of factors that protect against suicide. Further suicidal behavior among medically serious suicide attempters. The result of repeated exposure to such events for suicide, through the process of repeatedly experiencing painful events such as being suicidal in the workplace, is the loss of the instinctive fear of death, or what is often described as the survival instinct.⁹ Psychological theories are important theoretically and clinically because they provide a framework for understanding how complex factors combine to increase suicide risk. Adolescent suicide and suicidal behavior.

7. Prevalence

The prevalence of being exposed to suicide while on duty (including suicidal behaviors) ranged from 34.8% to 92.4%. Hom, Stanley reported the prevalence of suicide exposure (74%) in

⁸ Therefore, the main purpose of this study is to examine whether there is a difference in risk (depression, hopelessness, and mental pain) and psychiatric problems between individuals who try suicide and those who do not. A total of 11,806 students from seven provinces in China were recruited as potential participants.

⁹ Despite using IPTS-derived measures, no studies have compared the suicidal exposure theory assumption as a possible cause of suicide.

firefighters' personal lives rather than while on duty. They found that a greater emotional impact of suicide exposure was associated with a statistically significant higher lifetime risk of suicide attempt, suicide risk, depressive symptoms, nightmares, insomnia, and more severe PTSD symptoms. "Suicide and Suicidal Behavior among Transgender Persons". Past suicide attempts have been documented as one of the highest risk factors for another suicide attempt, with up to 20% of those trying re-attempts after the index attempt. One of the contributors to higher levels of psychological distress and VT among mental health professionals and first responders may be higher rates of suicide. The difference was significant ($U = 97,632.50$, $p < 0.001$). The effect size using Cohen's d was small (0.40). Suicide Attempt Risk The binary logistic regression model for the factors predicting suicide attempt was significant, $\chi^2(8) = 224.65$, $p < 0.001$, explaining 11.4% of the variance in suicide attempt (Nagelkerke R^2) and correctly classifying 98% of the cases.¹⁰ Although many risk factors have been identified, often failing to explain why people try to end their lives, it explains important recent developments in the theoretical, clinical, and empirical science of psychology about the occurrence of suicidal thoughts and behaviors, and it is necessary to emphasize the central importance of psychological factors.

There is also a need to better understand the risk factors and protective factors associated with suicide attempts. A better understanding of the factors that distinguish suicide attempts from those who are serious about it and those who have repeatedly tried suicide is necessary to integrate experimental, natural, clinical and non-clinical research findings. More innovative articles examine the core issue of therapeutic interventions for suicidal patients, with a particular focus on reducing suicide rates. Among youth, particularly college students, suicide is the second leading cause of death alongside self-injury, placing this population at risk, and the importance of research to better understand the threat cannot be overemphasized. For decades, clinical and theoretical explanations have described suicidal people as cognitively rigid or inflexible, leading to the conclusion that suicide is the only choice. Yet these two professional groups differ from each other in that mental health professionals often have formed a therapeutic alliance with the person who has died by suicide, and first responders are often unknown to the individual prior to suicide. Therefore, we suggest that exposure to suicide should be considered as a risk factor as more research is needed to examine the link between exposure and suicidality among first responders. Further, more in-depth research into the effects of suicide exposure among first responders is necessary to understand how exposure to suicide through work affects the individual.

More than 40 years ago, three psychologists came up with the eccentric, somewhat seductive headline "Lottery Winners and Accident Victims: Is Happiness Relative?" published a study entitled Even if you don't think you know what you're writing, there's a good chance you will. Earlier reports have supplied general assessments of the problem of suicidality and evaluate and synthesize current knowledge of the psychology of suicidal behavior, including psychological theories of suicidal behavior, risk and protective factors, and psychological interventions. Anxiety, loneliness, poor self-esteem, anger management problems (Peltzer,

¹⁰ Focusing on the differential effects of psychological factors on suicide risk as a function of age, culture, and ethnicity should be increased. Approximately 45% of individuals who died as a result of suicide consult a physician in particular without reporting their suicidal wishes and thoughts in the month before their death. Psychological Risk and Protective Factors associated with suicide risk can be classified into four groups: 1. Approximately 45% of individuals who died as a result of suicide consult a physician within one month of death, without reporting their suicidal thoughts and wishes.

Kleintjes, Wyk, Thompson, & Mashego, 2008) and academic difficulties that ultimately hinder subjective well-being have also been found (Oppong Asante, Kugbey, Osafo, Quarshie, & Sarfo, 2017) and potentially the occurrence of psychological distress and poor mental health as contributors to suicidal behavior.¹¹ Qualitative research has also shown that mental health professionals have an increased fear of suing after a patient's suicide. Gvion and Levi-Belz examined certain risk factors for serious suicide attempts (SSA). *Szücs et al. Integrating advances in psychological science into suicide prevention and intervention programs and developing public health interventions to foster resilience is important for low-income and middle-income countries as well as the development of interventions. Yet, compared to the depth of knowledge on suicide, risk, and prevention in the western world (Bridge, Goldstein, & Brent, 2006; Fontenella et al., 2015; Van Geel, Vedder, & Tanihon, 2014), the relative paucity of research on suicide in Africa (Adinkrah, et al). These study findings proved a strong dose-response relationship between the number of adverse events and the risk of later suicide attempts.* Based on the ten principles of cognitive theory, the model describes cognitive, emotional, behavioral, and physiological system features associated with the development of suicide risk by Williams (2001). A family history of suicide increases the risk of suicide; this effect is independent of a family history of mental disorders and thus suggests a partial social transference effect. Suicide among soldiers: A review of psychosocial risk and protective factors. Suicidal desire is a necessary reason, although not sufficient for a suicide attempt. It is the impact of exposure to suicide on these two professional groups (mental health professionals and first responders) that underpins this scoping review.

8. Negligence And Psychological Abuse

Negligence and psychological abuse were significantly associated with suicide risk, and this relationship was partially mediated by the maladaptive personality dimension of self-criticism. Relationship problems or loss, substance misuse; physical health problems; and job, money, legal or housing stress often contributed to risk for suicide.¹²

Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder Mental health professionals (especially psychiatrists) and first responders themselves also have high suicide rates. Those who tried suicide continued to report higher risk factor scores and lower protective factor scores, suggesting that they may continue to be more likely to try suicide. Theoretically informed research that focuses on understanding, not just explanation, is needed to advance our understanding of the context and risk of exposure to workplace suicide. Suicide is a public health problem of paramount importance given its lasting devastating effects on families, friends and communities.

Empirically Validated Interventions Country-specific empirically validated interventions should be informed by evidence-based research. *These findings relate to the fact that these professionals may have less training in mental health and suicide prevention than other*

¹¹ Over the last century, we have recognized the contribution of psychological factors (both individual and social) to suicide and suicide risk. Other Interpersonal Stressors After various interpersonal stressors control the risk of suicidal behavior and even the effects of mental disorders, interpersonal stressors can take various forms and more diverse types of stressors have been associated with suicidal behavior, including romantic problems, legal difficulties, loss of income, non-straight orientation and bullying, victimization.

¹² They found that emotional intelligence as a mediator was associated with psychological distress and suicide risk. In addition, exposure to suicide appears to be associated with suicide risk among first responders and should be the focus of the suicide prevention protocol.

professional categories. *Suicide Risk Management A Manual for Health Professionals (2nd ed.)*. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons. *Cognitive Vulnerability and Suicide as Self-Escape Cognitive vulnerability (for example, social problem solving) explains the relationship between stress and suicide risk*. Other studies, not focusing specifically on suicidal behavior, have found worrying prevalence rates (mild, moderate, and severe), inadequate social support, substance abuse, self-stigmatization, and traumatic life events among college students (Andoh-Arthur, Oppong Asante, & Osafo, 2015; Oppong Asante & Andoh-Arthur, 2015). Therefore, it is important to evaluate how young people with a history of suicide attempt function psychologically, to better understand the causes of suicide attempts and to develop suicide prevention strategies. The critical incident review of safety procedures taken by professionals prior to suicide has been reported to be a distressing event, potentially worsening the effects of exposure to suicide. Counselors and Social Workers The only article among counselors and social workers (USA) reporting the effects of suicide exposure reported that 82.7% of the sample was a patient attempt or complete suicide. In addition, this literature has not been reviewed together as a case of occupational-based suicide exposure and its effects. Emotional responses described by professionals included sadness, shock, surprise, blame, despair, guilt, self-doubt, grief, and anger.¹³ QoL significantly mediates the associations between emotional difficulties and peer problems, as both are associated with lower QoL, which in turn appears to be associated with a higher risk of suicide. "Suicide among heroin users: rates, risk factors and methods". "Dialectical behavior therapy in adolescents for suicide prevention: systematic review of clinical-effectiveness". *Overall, the most common professional response to exposure to suicide was increased awareness of suicide risk in patients. Suicide and suicidal behaviour. "Suicide and suicidal behavior". "Screening for and treatment of suicide risk relevant to primary care: a systematic review for the US Preventive Services Task Force". The trap has also been shown to predict repeated suicide attempts over a 4-year period beyond traditional risk markers. Research findings reveal that those who try suicide show higher fearlessness of injury and death than controls who do not commit suicide, and this difference may explain why men are more likely to die by suicide than women.*¹⁴ *Suicide can be seen as a behavior motivated by the desire to escape unbearable psychological pain. Regarding reasons to live, a 10-year follow-up study found that psychiatric outpatients with a moderate-to-strong will to die and little will to live were at increased risk of suicide.*

9. The World Health Organization Estimates

The World Health Organization estimates that there are approximately 25 cases of suicide attempts for every suicide death. Suicide can be seen as a behavior motivated by an overwhelming desire to escape psychological pain. For example, clinical trials testing dialectical behavioral therapy (in patients with borderline personality disorder) and cognitive therapy (in those who have recently attempted suicide) have supplied support for the

¹³ Therefore, it is the responsibility of psychologists, psychiatrists and relevant mental health professionals to understand suicide and develop methods to predict and prevent its occurrence. Future research will decide whether positive future thought and suicide attempts change over time and whether the content of positive future thought influences the degree to which positive thoughts are protective.

¹⁴ However, the precise nature of the association is unclear, as evidence suggests that suicide risk is associated with abnormal cortisol concentrations or a maladaptive cortisol response to stress. examined quality of life (QoL) as a factor that may serve as a link between psychopathology and suicide risk among a clinical adolescent population.

effectiveness of these treatments to reduce the rate of suicide reattempts compared to others. Beyond the mental pain: a case-control study on the contribution of schizoid personality disorder symptoms to medically serious suicide attempts.¹⁵

There is a need for research that addresses the issue of exposure to suicide among these professionals and focuses on its emotional and occupational effects. The groundbreaking work of Emile Durkheim laid the foundations for our understanding that suicide is also a social behavior with more cultural characteristics. However, exposure to suicide only during the seizure was associated with an increased risk of suicide in these firefighters. Findings from psychological autopsy studies show that more than 90% of people who die by suicide have a psychiatric disorder before they die. A Global Health and Social Issue Suicide is a global health and social problem, and an estimated 800,000 people die by suicide each year. Regarding the reassessment of career choices, questioning one's career choice is not limited to health professionals and has been seen in other professions dealing with emotionally sensitive content, such as suicide researchers. Those who tried suicide reported higher Median scores for all three risk factor measures. "Risk factors for suicide in the transgender community". No studies have reported measures of suicide risk among psychologists and psychiatrists exposed to suicide. This finding is consistent with the continuum approach, and the risk of suicide increases as the individual attempts to think and plan. The results show that the group that tried suicide had a higher risk of suicide than the group that did not try suicide. The relationship between suicide ideation, behavioral health, and college academic performance. Recent reports report that approximately one million people die by suicide each year, representing the annual global age-standardized suicide rate of 11.4 (15.0 for men and 8.0 for women) per 100,000 population.

Considering a time perspective from 2000 to 2016, there has been a 30% increase in suicide rates by age.

These ratios are just the tip of an iceberg.¹⁶ There is minimal research on these strategies. conducted a systematic review of randomized controlled trials that reported that therapeutic interventions were effective in reducing self-harm, including suicide attempts. Most studies were conducted in the USA, other studies UK, Australia, Ireland, France, Belgium, Italy No research from other countries All articles evaluating suicide exposure used web surveys. Changes in professional practice after a patient's suicide include increased awareness of suicide risk, decreased confidence, and more restrictive practices, including increased monitoring and detention for nurses. Adolescents who reported lower social support from their parents, peers, and school were more likely to have a history of suicide attempts. Finding suicide risk among college students: a systematic review.¹⁷ *Recent research suggests that agitation predicts suicide attempts, especially in people with high suicidality. Peer Review Reports Suicide has become a*

¹⁵ Emile Durkheim's seminal work laid the foundations for our understanding that suicide is also a social behavior with more cultural characteristics. The professional responses described showed that suicide risk and increased awareness of suicide cues were the most common effects on professional practice.

¹⁶ Other suicide prevention strategies that have been considered are crisis centers and hotlines, method control, and media education..

¹⁷ One explanation for the higher suicide rates among these occupations is higher levels of occupational psychological distress and work-related Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) for first responders. However, more evidence in college students suggests that people with high optimism have a reduced risk of suicidal ideation or try when faced with serious or moderately negative life events, compared with people with low optimism. Thus, although the presence and accumulation of psychiatric disorders are risk factors for suicidal behavior, they have little predictive power and, perhaps more importantly, do not explain why people try to kill themselves.

major public health problem with 800,000 deaths per year. "Suicide risk in relation to socioeconomic, demographic, psychiatric, and familial factors: a national register-based study of all suicides in Denmark, 1981–1997". It is important to have information about the psychological factors that affect the preference of one suicide method over another. Although impulsivity has been studied for decades, the association with suicide risk is not as consistent or straightforward as originally thought, and its impact may be less direct. Perhaps more importantly, this mental association with death warrants further investigation as it predicts future suicide attempts by clinicians or patients. For example, focusing on the life events of adolescents and young adults, as well as college-aged students (i.e., 18- to 24-year-olds in China) can be instrumental in increasing our understanding of factors associated with suicidal behavior. As the ability develops, testing of psychological theories of suicide risk should be the rule rather than the exception. Due to the lack of research among paramedics and ambulance personnel, we cannot draw conclusions about the effects of exposure to suicide among these professionals. While more researchers report that the relationship between negative life events and suicidal behavior is mediated by the presence of mental disorders, other study findings do not support this explanation. Suicide risk screening: comparing the Beck depression inventory-II, Beck hopelessness scale, and Psychache scale in undergraduates. The risk of suicide increases when feelings of defeat and entrapment are high and the potential for recovery (e.g., social support) is low. Most people who struggle with suicidal thoughts and behaviors do not seek treatment.

10. Personality and Individual Differences

Although more risk factors have been found, they often do not explain why people try to end their lives. The difference was significant ($U = 97,582.00$, $p < 0.001$). The effect size using Cohen's d is small (0.40). Purpose in Life Mean score of the group who tried suicide in the measurement for life purpose was 18.2 ± 5.1 and Median score of 19 (min = 4, max= 28), Mean score of those who did not try suicide is 20.4 ± 4.6 and the Median score is 21 (4. So, if Brickman was suffering from an underlying condition, as Rabinowitz argues, there was obviously too much hiding. Predicting precisely who will die by suicide has long eluded mental health professionals. "Air Pollution (Particulate Matter) Exposure and Associations with Depression, Anxiety, Bipolar, Psychosis and Suicide Risk: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis". His professional responses ranged from increased awareness of suicide risk, decreased professional confidence, fear of publicity and lawsuits, increased referrals to psychiatrists, and workplace sadness. For a sample range, including older adults, and people with chronic pain, perceived burdensome has also been shown to mediate the relationship between perfectionism and suicidal ideation, and continued to predict thought even after controlling for factors such as depression and hopelessness.

While reliable and official statistics on suicide among university students in Ghana are lacking, more studies supply insight into the risks for better understanding of events among this group.¹⁸ A narrative review of the relationship between victimization, depression and suicide ideation among lesbian, gay and bisexual individuals. Borderline personality disorder and eating disorders have been reported as comorbid antecedents of suicide attempts. Although psychological mechanisms (e.g., modeling effects) need more experimental research, media

¹⁸ The most common professional change was nurses' increased awareness of suicide risk among patients.

depictions of suicide may affect suicide rates. Such studies have found several cognitive factors that appear to increase the risk of suicidal behavior. Although 60% of the world's suicides occur in Asia, psychological suicide is still dominated by research in populations in Western Europe, the USA, and Canada. Suicidal thinking and behavior among youth involved in verbal and social bullying: Risk and protective factors. Suicide studies should routinely include psychological components, especially when it comes to large-scale nationally linked studies of suicide and suicide attempts. In addition, distress/trauma led to suicide through an increased risk of psychosis, as proved by cognitive symptoms. Associations between depression, anxiety, stress, hopelessness, subjective well-being, coping styles and suicide in Chinese university students.¹⁹ Personality and individual differences, cognitive factors, social aspects and negative life events are factors that contribute to suicidal behavior. The emotional effects reported were related to the news of suicide and fear of being sued, 19.8% reported distress after the suicide press release, and 44.5% of professionals were distressed by the prospect of litigation. Personality and individual differences, cognitive factors, social aspects and negative life events contribute significantly to suicidal behavior. Hence, the increasing concentration of research on finding risk factors for suicidal ideation and attempts (Osman et al., 1998).²⁰

11. Conclusions

A meta-analysis of longitudinal studies by Soto-Sanz et al found that youth with lower self-esteem were up to twice as likely to try suicide in the future. Perfectionism can be defined in diverse ways and is not equally associated with the risk of all types of suicide. "Screening for suicide risk in adolescents, adults, and older adults in primary care: US Preventive Services Task Force recommendation statement". Rodriguez and colleagues found that those who did not try self-harm and had a significantly higher life purpose compared to patients who tried suicide. Childhood sexual and physical abuse is a particularly strong risk.

*Like anxiety, these outcomes are associated with suicide risk. In addition, considering the WHO's announcement that suicide rates will exceed the one million marks in the next 15 years, it is predicted that suicide rates will increase in the future.*²¹

Behind every suicide and attempt, there is a long-term struggle of these individuals, their experiences of trauma and distress among their relatives and friends. "Suicide and suicide risk in lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender populations: review and recommendations". Exploratory path models about the associations between suicide ideation, depression, interpersonal difficulties, and self-esteem among young adults. For most groups, the effects of exposure to suicide have been reported in the personal and professional domains. Reconnecting

¹⁹ Risk Taking and Decision-Making Suicide is the 14th leading cause of death worldwide, responsible for 1.5% of all deaths. He was also the first to review the literature on the effects of suicide exposure on first responders. While most studies were unable to decide the efficacy of therapeutic interventions for both primary and secondary outcomes, individual self-directed and socially driven processes seemed to offer the greatest hope in reducing suicide attempts.

²⁰ However, there are exceptions; In the 18-year follow-up of depressed patients, neuroticism did not predict future suicide risk.

²¹ Sequence factors for both the onset and persistence of suicidal behavior and the risk of suicidal behavior are especially high in childhood and adolescence, and the relationship between childhood adversities and suicidal behavior decreases with age.

with oneself while struggling between life and death: the phenomenon of recovery as experienced by persons at risk of suicide.

Gatekeeper suicide training's effectiveness among Malaysian hospital health professionals: a control group study with a three-month follow-up. First, there was a complete lack of research on exposure to suicide among paramedics and ambulance workers. Suicide can be decided by the interaction of numerous factors such as neurobiology, personal or family history, stressful events, and sociocultural environment. "Lithium treatment and suicide risk in major affective disorders: update and new findings". "Annual Research Review: A meta-analytic review of worldwide suicide rates in adolescents". *Predictive value of psychological characteristics and suicide history on medical lethality of suicide attempts: a follow-up study of hospitalized patients. Those who tried suicide reported significantly lower Median scores for all three measures of protective factor compared with those who did not try suicide.* Moreover, most people experience more type of negative life event at more point in their lives, but do not engage in suicidal behavior; this highlights the importance of considering how vulnerability factors and stressors might interact to produce suicidal behavior, as theoretical models suggest. Cipriano et al conducted a recent systematic review of suicide attempts focusing on epidemiological, etiological, and diagnostic criteria. Risk factors Few studies have examined risk factors for suicidal behavior in certain populations. Correlates of suicide risk among secondary school students in Cape Town. The role of hopelessness and meaning in life in a clinical sample with non-suicidal self-injury and suicide attempts.

This modest estimate of 25 attempted suicides²² for every suicide death gives us an estimate that 20 million people attempt suicide annually.²³ Consequently, it is essential in this special issue to aim to improve knowledge about suicide by identifying specific psychological characteristics that can facilitate targeted prevention, intervention methods and programs. Findings from studies in which behavioral tests of cognitive rigidity were applied to those who tried suicide and from clinical controls supported this view. In a classic study, Beck and colleagues were able to predict 91% of all suicides due to blocked belonging.

However, findings from a 12-year prospective Finnish study showed that hopelessness was a non-significant predictor of suicide compared with hopelessness (in a sample of 224 suicide attempts). Barriers to seeking help and the role of the media (including social media) in the suicide process are also poorly understood; Although there are media guidelines on suicide reports, more empirical evidence is needed on which aspects of reporting are most dangerous. The aim of this study was to explore the psychological understanding of the phenomenon of suicide as well as non-suicidal self-harm (suicide attempts).²⁴ Suicide ideation and depression in university students in Botswana. When the pain becomes unbearable: case-control study of mental pain characteristics among medically serious suicide attempters. Social factors Suicide does not happen in a social vacuum. Predicting future suicide attempts among adolescent and emerging adult psychiatric emergency patients. Mental pain, communication difficulties, and medically serious suicide attempts: a case-control study. Interpersonal-Psychological Model

²² For every suicide death, about 135 other people experience significant adverse effects. It may not be significant in all cases of suicide risk, but it is more likely to be clear in the young than in the elderly.

²³ Risk factors are events or situations that are positively associated with suicidal behavior.

²⁴ And the period when a person is at highest risk of dying by suicide is at once after leaving a psychiatric institution. ($U = 170,489.00$, $p < 0.001$). The effect size using Cohen's d is small (0.28). Self-respect For self-esteem, the mean score of the group who tried suicide was $25.4 \pm \pm 3.9$ and Median score of 25 (min = 12, max = 37), Mean score of those who did not try suicide is $27.3 \pm \pm 3.7$ and a Median score .

Joiner (2005))¹⁵ The suicidal urge results from an elevated level of burden and inhibition of belonging.

An appraisal model suggesting that risk arises from the interaction between biases in information processing, schema, and evaluation systems is summarized by Wenzel and Beck (2008) as a cognitive model of suicidal behavior. Subjective psychological well-being (WHO-5) in assessment of the severity of suicide attempt. Theoretically, this study examines suicide from the perspective of the human ecological model to understand the occurrence of suicide among university students. Therefore, for this population, attitudes towards suicide can be understood as one of the factors shaping self-assessment and life satisfaction. Police officers have the highest exposure to suicide, followed by firefighters, psychiatrists, counselors, social workers and psychologists the lowest. Suicide communication on social media and its psychological mechanisms: an examination of Chinese microblog users. Nock, professor of psychology at Harvard and the nation's leading scientist on suicide, conducted a famous study in 2010 that showed that clinicians in a major city psychiatric emergency room were no better at guessing who is with a coin flip after leaving their care. Amid the downward trend in suicide rates in China over the past 20 years, an increase in suicide deaths among young adults has been reported. More research is needed on this phenomenon, particularly among police, firefighters, and ambulance workers/medical workers, given that going to a suicide scene can increase related outcomes.²⁵

Most suicides are brutal mysteries, the "private and inexpressible" pain of the deceased, as Kay Redfield Jamison put it in his 1999 masterpiece "The Night Is Falling: Understanding Suicide." However, Brickman wrote more than 50 book chapters and academic articles in his short life, as well as a book published posthumously. However, impulsivity should still be considered when assessing the risk of suicide or self-harm. Global Health Observatory data repository: suicide rates estimate, crude. They also suggested using (history of attempt) scores or SBQ-R total scores to develop subgroups of individuals with a history of suicide attempt/attempt and never tried suicide: Suicide Attempt Group. 39% of those who reported having been exposed to suicide during their personal lives said, "that he was affected by suicide" but" He stated that it was not at a level that would turn my life upside down. As such, it seems to ignore psychologists and psychiatrists as potentially more at risk of suicide. Mood has also been found to prove diagnostic accuracy for sign of earlier and recent suicide attempts among undergraduates.

12. Results

Above all, our mission is to advance our knowledge by understanding the mechanisms, factors, and facilitators of suicide from interdisciplinary perspectives. Therefore, more specific markers of suicide risk need to be defined. This group of professionals are often the first to be involved in a suspected suicide event, which is described as one of the most critical and traumatic situations first responders can meet during their work. *For example, in one chart study of 76 patients who died by suicide on admission, 79% had severe anxiety or agitation shortly before*

²⁵ Any risk of suicide should naturally assess how socially isolated a vulnerable individual is. Well-being and social capital: Do suicide pose a puzzle? Social Indicators Research, 81, 455–496. A meta-analysis by Ribeiro and colleagues showed that individuals with hopelessness and depression had a weighted mean odds ratio of 1.63 (95% CI 1.55–1.72) to try suicide.

*their death. Suicide prevention on college campuses: what works and what are the existing gaps?*²⁶ The results showed that the incidence of suicide peaks in the spring and around Christmas, emphasizing the importance of health care accessibility during these high-risk moments. While defeat and entrapment are good, the fixed structures in the Psychopathology literature offer important hope for applications in suicide research. A fourth limitation found in the literature is the lack of definition of the relationship between healthcare professionals and the patient who died by suicide (e.g., case manager, psychotherapist, or prescriber). It is important for those who have tried suicide to understand and prevent future attempts. "Animal Suicide Sheds Light on Human Behavior". Finally, psychological science has more offer policy planners in the development and implementation of suicide prevention programs. Therefore, the two-pronged specific aims of the study were to decide the lifetime and current prevalence of suicidal ideation or attempts; It is necessary to find the associated risks and protective factors. But the most common feature among people who die by suicide are symptoms of mental illness. The higher the level of on-duty suicide exposure, the more likely officers were to report a PTSD diagnosis, suggesting that taking part in suicide scenes had a specific PTSD effect. In reviewing these factors, we summarize what is known to date, but do not fully describe the potential mechanisms by which these factors may influence suicidal behavior, an extremely important target for future research. Suicide attempts were found to be most common among adolescents and young adults. Female professionals and those who felt more responsible for the patient's death had more pronounced emotional reactions at once after a patient's suicide. Impulsivity may be useful in predicting recurrent suicide attempts in individuals with personality disorders. This explains important recent developments in the theoretical, clinical, and empirical science of psychology about the occurrence of suicidal thoughts and behaviors, and it is necessary to emphasize the vital importance of psychological factors. Suicide and Life-Threatening Behavior, 33, 165–171. Suicide & Life-Threatening Behavior. Suicide & Life-Threatening Behavior. Suicide and Life-Threatening Behavior. "What Distinguishes Suicide Attempters from Suicide Ideates? A Meta-Analysis of Potential Factors". "Lithium in the prevention of suicide in mood disorders: updated systematic review and meta-analysis".

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